

Electrochemical and spectral studies of binuclear monohydroxo-bridged copper(II) complexes

Krishna Srivastava*, Ashish Kumar Srivastava and Jagdish Prasad

Department of Chemistry, University of Allahabad, Allahabad-211 002, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : dr_krishna_s@yahoo.co.in

Manuscript received 10 September 2007, revised 16 September 2008, accepted 17 September 2008

Abstract : The electrochemical behavior of μ -hydroxo-tetrakis(2,2'-bipyridine)dicopper(II) perchlorate, $[(bipy)_2Cu(\mu-OH)Cu(bipy)_2](ClO_4)_3$, 1 and μ -hydroxo-tetrakis(1,10-phenanthroline)dicopper(II) perchlorate, $(phen)_2Cu(\mu-OH)Cu(phen)_2(ClO_4)_3$, 2 has been studied in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethylformamide (DMF) and acetonitrile (AN) containing 0.2 M sodium perchlorate at a glassy carbon working electrode (GCE) at 25 °C using cyclic voltammetry. Both these complexes undergo a diffusion-controlled single-electron quasi-reversible electrode process. The value of formal electrode potentials, E^0 for complex 1 are 80 mV and 145 mV vs Ag/AgCl in DMSO and DMF, respectively. The coulometry performed at -170 mV vs Ag/AgCl in the case of light blue solution of complex 1 in DMSO containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ yielded an intense red solution involving a single electron transfer per molecule of complex ($Cu^{II}Cu^{II} \xrightleftharpoons[-e]{+e} Cu^{II}Cu^I$). The cyclic voltammograms of the red coloured mixed-valent complex solution were also recorded, giving a quasi-reversible anodic couple (Cu^+/Cu^{2+}) with E^0 about 50 mV vs Ag/AgCl. The red solution, on keeping overnight, turned light greenish-blue in colour. The CV experiments with this light greenish-blue solution, result in a quasi-reversible cathodic couple (Cu^{2+}/Cu^+) with E^0 about 50 mV. On the basis of our present electrochemical studies it is found that the redox potentials of 1 and 2 are strongly dependent on the organic solvents. The electronic spectra of these complexes were also recorded in DMSO, DMF and AN.

Keywords : Electrochemistry, cyclic voltammetry, hydroxo-bridged binuclear copper(II) complexes, bipyridine, phenanthroline.

Introduction

The study of binuclear complexes of copper(II) is a very active and highly interesting field due to their significance in bioinorganic chemistry, magnetochemistry, material science, multimetal centre catalysis, superconductivity and multielectron redox chemistry¹. Hydroxo-bridged binuclear copper(II) complexes have been found² to be catalytically active for oxidative coupling reactions.

The cyclic voltammetric studies of antiferromagnetically coupled square pyramidal binuclear copper(II) complexes with pentadentate L-proline-based binucleating ligands containing bridging moieties (OH^- , $MeCO_2^-$, NO_2^- and N_3^-) revealed^{3a} the presence of two redox couples $Cu^{II}Cu^{II} \xrightleftharpoons[-e]{+e} Cu^{II}Cu^I$ and Cu^ICu^I . Electrochemical and spectral properties of some monohydroxo-bridged binuclear Cu^{II} complexes with different exogenous bridging motifs have also revealed^{3b} the existence of two reduction couples $Cu^{II}Cu^{II}/Cu^{II}Cu^I$ and Cu^ICu^I/Cu^ICu^I .

Thomson *et al.*⁴ have reported that a binuclear antiferromagnetically coupled hydroxo-bridged five-coordinated copper(II) complex of a hexadentate (N_6) phthalazine ligand undergoes two-electron oxidation at + 0.50 V vs SCE to form a binuclear copper(III) derivative. The pair of irreversible reduction waves observed in the CV of the di- μ -hydroxocopper(II) complex of L¹ correspond to sequential one-electron reductions of the dicopper centre⁵. Hendrickson *et al.*⁶ reported an electrochemical study of the triply bridged, ferromagnetically coupled dinuclear copper(II) complex, $[Cu_2(OH)(H_2O)(OAc)(bipy)_2](ClO_4)_2$ in acetonitrile gave only an irreversible and poorly defined wave.

In this paper we have reported the electrochemical and electronic spectral properties of two monohydroxo-bridged binuclear copper(II) complexes with diimine ligands. X-Ray crystal structure determination of complex 1 revealed⁷ that it consists of two approximately

trigonal-bipyramidal Cu^{II} centers, wherein the bridging oxygen atom of hydroxide ion occupies an equatorial site on each copper atom while the remaining sites are filled by the nitrogen atoms of the bipyridine ligands (Figs. 1(a,b)).

Fig. 1(a). View of the binuclear cation [(bipy)₂Cu-OH-Cu(bipy)₂]³⁺ with the hydrogen atom omitted for clarity. The various pyridine moieties are labeled A, A', etc.

Fig. 1(b). Coordination geometry about the copper(II) ions in [(bipy)₂Cu-OH-Cu(bipy)₂]³⁺. Atoms NA and NA' are nitrogen atoms of pyridine groups A and A', respectively, and are parts of the same bipyridine ligand etc.

Results and discussion

The electrochemical properties of two approximately trigonal bipyramidal binuclear copper(II) complexes bridged by only a single hydroxide ion, viz. μ -hydroxo-tetrakis(2,2'-bipyridine)dicopper(II) perchlorate, [(bipy)₂Cu(μ -OH)Cu(bipy)₂](ClO₄)₃, **1**; μ -hydroxo-tetrakis(1,10-phenanthroline)dicopper(II) perchlorate, [(phen)₂Cu(μ -OH)Cu(phen)₂](ClO₄)₃, **2** where, bipy = 2,2'-bipyridine and phen = 1,10-phenanthroline have been investigated in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO), dimethylformamide (DMF) and acetonitrile (AN) containing 0.2

M NaClO₄ at a glassy carbon disc working electrode (GCE) by measuring their cyclic voltammograms (CV) with scan rate (ν) ranging from 25 to 500 mV s⁻¹. The cyclic voltammograms of complexes **1** and **2** in DMSO, DMF and AN containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ in the potential range +1000 to -450 mV are displayed in Figs. 2(a to f) and the CV data for these complexes are listed in

Table 1. CV data for 1 mM [(bipy)₂Cu(μ -OH)Cu(bipy)₂](ClO₄)₃ in nonaqueous solvents containing 0.2 M NaClO₄

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{pa} (mV)	E _{pc} (mV)	E ⁰ (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I _{pc} /I _{pa}
In DMSO :					
25	40	127	83.5	87	0.9
50	39	128	83.5	89	0.9
100	32	134	83.0	102	0.9
200	25	137	81.0	112	0.9
300	25	139	82.0	114	0.9
400	22	141	81.5	119	0.9
500	19	144	81.5	125	0.9
In DMF :					
25	83	194	138.5	111	1.0
50	77	195	136.0	118	1.0
100	80	198	139.0	118	1.0
200	96	203	149.5	107	0.9
300	101	203	152.0	102	0.9
400	102	203	152.5	101	0.8
500	104	205	154.5	101	0.8
In AN :					
25	8	118	63.0	110	1.2
50	7	113	60.0	106	1.2
100	6	113	59.5	107	1.2
200	0	115	57.5	115	1.3
300	1	114	57.5	113	1.5
400	1	115	57.0	114	1.4
500	-1	116	57.5	117	1.4

Table 2. CV data for 1 mM [(phen)₂Cu(μ -OH)Cu(phen)₂](ClO₄)₃ in nonaqueous solvents containing 0.2 M NaClO₄

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E _{pc} (mV)	E _{pa} (mV)	E ⁰ (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I _{pa} /I _{pc}
In DMSO :					
25	33	134	83.5	101	1.1
50	21	144	82.5	123	1.1
100	11	150	80.5	139	1.1
200	-2	160	79.0	162	0.8
300	-11	160	74.5	171	0.9
400	-17	167	75.0	184	0.8

Table-2 (contd)					
500	-26	172	73 0	198	0 7
In DMF					
25	26	183	104 5	157	1 4
50	27	189	108 0	162	4 6
100	-	193	-	-	-
200	-	200	-	-	-
300	-	201	-	-	-
400	-	204	-	-	-
500	-	208	-	-	-
In AN					
25	-307	114	-	-	-
50	-312	115	-	-	-
100	-312	111	-	-	-
200	-332	121	-	-	-
300	-339	120	-	-	-
400	-348	127	-	-	-
500	-357	130	-	-	-

Tables 1 and 2, respectively. These complexes reveal a single redox couple corresponding to the redox process except complex 2 in acetonitrile where ill-defined irreversible multiple overlapping waves are observed (Fig. 2(f)).

Controlled potential coulometry of both complexes 1 and 2 at -170 and -190 mV vs Ag/AgCl respectively, in DMSO/ $0.2 M NaClO_4$ confirms the involvement of one-electron per molecule in this reduction process⁸. Analysis of CV data for the $Cu^{II}Cu^{II}-Cu^{II}Cu^I$ couple with scan rates ranging from 25 to 500 mV s^{-1} showed the following characteristic. For complexes 1 and 2, the peak current ratio (I_{pa}/I_{pc}) is 1.0 in DMSO, indicating that the electrode process involves a simple single-electron transfer reaction without any chemical complication⁸, the anodic to cathodic peak potential difference, ΔE_p ranges from

Fig. 2. Cyclic voltammograms of complex 1 in DMSO (a), DMF (b), AN (c) and complex 2 in DMSO (d), DMF (e), AN (f).

80–125 mV (for 1) and 101–198 mV (for 2) and the cathodic peak potential (E_{pc}) becomes more negative (or less positive) with increasing scan rate, showing that the electrode process is quasi-reversible⁸. Plot of I_{pc} vs $v^{1/2}$ gives straight line without any intercept, showing that the reduction process is diffusion-controlled. It is noteworthy that the cathodic peak (E_{pc}) for complex 2 in DMF is comparatively broad and its peak potentials were not recordable at $v \geq 100$ mV s⁻¹ (Fig. 1e). Interestingly, however, the cyclic voltammograms of complex 2 in AN show three ill defined overlapping waves, clearly indicating that this complex decomposes in this medium. It may be noted that the peak current ratio (I_{pa}/I_{pc}) is more than unity for complex 1 in AN and for 2 in DMSO and AN, clearly showing that the electrochemically generated reduced species is weakly adsorbed⁸ at the surface of the working electrode (GCE). Similar observations^{9a} has earlier been made for mixed ligand Cu^{II} complexes of 1,10-phenanthroline and aminoacids.

It should be noted that the reduction potentials of these complexes are solvent dependent (Tables 1 and 2). It is important to note that electrochemical studies of square pyramidal monohydroxo-bridged binuclear copper(II) complexes exhibited³ two successive and distinct mono-electronic quasi reversible reduction steps. The first and second couples appeared at $E^O = +230$ to -318 mV and $E^O = -419$ to -1046 mV vs Ag/AgCl, respectively.

A perusal of Tables 1 and 2 shows that the cathodic peak potential (E_{pc}) is more positive for the bipy complex 1 than the phen complex 2 in a given solvent, indicating that the reduction of 1 is easier than that of 2. This is contrary to our observations^{9(a,b)} in the case of mixed ligand copper(II) complexes involving bipy/phen and aminoacids. It should be mentioned that the redox potentials of complexes are affected by various factors^{3,10}, such as types of ligands, nature of donor atoms, geometry of the complex, electron density on the central metal ion, solvent etc.

Furthermore, a constant potential electrolysis of complex 1 in DMSO turned the colour of solution from bluish green to dark red. The anodic scan initiated at -300 mV of this red solution in the potential range -300 to 1000 mV, yields a quasi-reversible, diffusion-controlled single-electron transfer reaction with $E^O = 50$ mV vs Ag/AgCl and $I_{pc}/I_{pa} = 1.0$, $\Delta E_p = 77$ – 120 mV (Table

3). After keeping the red solution overnight and deoxygenation, CVs were again recorded of the resulting bluish-green solution (cathodic scan) in the same potential region and almost similar results as for the red solution (Table 4) was obtained. It may, therefore, be concluded that the oxidized and reduced form of the bipy complex 1 are stable under the time window of cyclic voltammetric as well as bulk electrolysis experiments.

Table 3. CV data for reduced form of [(bipy)₂Cu(μ-OH)Cu(bipy)₂](ClO₄)₃ in DMSO containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ after bulk electrolysis (dark red solution)-anodic scan (+)

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	E^O (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pc}/I_{pa}
25	88	11	49.5	77	1.0
50	93	8	50.5	85	1.0
100	94	8	51.0	86	0.9
200	101	-1	50.0	102	1.0
300	100	-5	47.5	105	1.0
400	103	-6	48.5	109	1.0
500	107	-13	47.0	120	1.0

Table 4. CV data for reduced form of [(bipy)₂Cu(μ-OH)Cu(bipy)₂](ClO₄)₃ in DMSO containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ after bulk electrolysis and keeping the red solution overnight (greenish blue solution)-cathodic scan (-)

Scan rate (mV s ⁻¹)	E_{pc} (mV)	E_{pa} (mV)	E^O (mV)	ΔE_p (mV)	I_{pa}/I_{pc}
25	10	89	49.5	79	1.1
50	6	95	50.5	89	0.8
100	4	97	50.5	93	1.0
200	-7	103	48.0	110	1.0
300	-5	105	49.5	110	0.8
400	-7	106	49.5	113	0.8
500	-12	109	48.5	121	0.9

The electronic absorption spectra of complexes 1 and 2 in DMSO, DMF and AN show a low-intensity band in the 650–710 nm region due to the *d-d* transition, except for complex 2 in DMF (red coloured) where a very intense charge transfer band at 442 nm appeared (Table 5).

Table 5. Electronic absorption spectral data λ_{max} , nm (ϵ , L mol⁻¹cm⁻¹) for complexes 1 and 2 in DMSO, DMF and AN

Complex	Solvent		
	DMSO	DMF	AN
1	703 (75)	699 (110)	681 (150)
2	664 (105)	442 (22590)	690 (135)

Experimental

The complexes **1** and **2** were prepared according to procedure described⁷ earlier and their purity was checked by elemental analyses. All reagents used were of analytical grade. The nonaqueous solutions (DMSO, DMF and AN) of the complexes under investigation were freshly prepared.

The software driven BAS Electrochemical System, Model EPSILON (Bioanalytical Systems, Inc, USA) was employed for all the electrochemical studies. 1×10^{-2} M stock solutions of these complexes were prepared in the desired solvent. More dilute (1×10^{-3} M) solutions were prepared by accurate dilution. The working electrode was glassy carbon disc electrode (GCE), the counter electrode was a platinum wire and reference electrode Ag/AgCl in saturated KCl ($E^0 = +199$ mV vs NHE). Purging and blanketing of nitrogen (99.999% pure) were done for analyte solution placed in the electrochemical cell of 15 ml capacity for 20 min. Great care was taken in the electrode pretreatment. Mechanical polishing of the working electrode (GCE) was done over a velvet microcloth with an alumina suspension. Controlled Potential Electrolysis (CPE) was carried out for calculating the number of electrons involved in the reduction process. Electrolysis was done in 1×10^{-3} M DMSO solution of a complex containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ in a BASi Bulk electrolysis cell consisting of Reticulated Carbon Working Electrode, coiled platinum auxiliary electrode dipped in a separate cell containing 0.2 M NaClO₄ in DMSO solution only and Ag/AgCl as a reference electrode. Nitrogen gas was initially purged for 30 min with constant stirring the solution and then N₂ was blanketed over the constantly stirred cell solution during the electrolysis. All the electrochemical experiments were performed at a constant temperature 25 ± 0.5 °C. Room temperature electronic absorption spectra of complexes **1** and **2** were measured in the range 800–400 nm with a Perkin-Elmer UV-Visible spectrophotometer Model Lambda 35 available in our laboratory, for 2 mM solutions in DMSO, DMF and AN.

Acknowledgement

The authors (JP and KS) are grateful to Defence Research and Development Organisation (DRDO), Ministry of Defence, Government of India for sanctioning a research project.

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